

USE OF ATTRIBUTE SELECTION AND CLASSIFICATION FOR THE PREDICTION OF DIABETES CONDITION

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Abstract

Diabetes is a disorder that arises when the pancreas fails to generate sufficient insulin or when the human body does not utilize the insulin that is produced. Insulin is a type of hormone that controls sugar levels in the blood. Hyperglycemia, or high blood sugar, is a typical side effect of untreated diabetes, and it can cause catastrophic harm to many of the systems that comprise the body, particularly the neurons and vessels that carry blood. This experiment was carried out to select important attributes for the prediction of diabetic conditions by making use of machine learning algorithms. It has been concluded that if we use the SVM supervised attribute selection method with a ranker and Naïve Bayes classifier, it works well for the prediction of diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes, Attribute Selection, Correlation SVM, J48, Naïve Bayes, Classification

1.Introduction

According to the report by the World Health Organization, an estimated 77 million individuals in India over the age of 18 have diabetes of some kind, and almost 25 million are in prediabetic conditions with a higher risk of becoming diabetic in the near future. Most diabetic patients are ignorant of their condition, which can lead to serious health issues if not diagnosed and treated early. Diabetes increases the risk of heart attack and kidney disease by two to three times in adults. Neuropathy in the feet, when combined with restricted blood flow, raises the risk of ulcers in the feet, an infection, and ultimately the necessity for an amputation of a limb. Diabetes-associated retinopathy is a leading cause of blindness that results from long-term harm to the retina's tiny blood vessels [1][2]. Diabetes is one of the most common causes of renal failure. The National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases provided the source data for this dataset. The dataset's goal is to diagnose whether or not a patient has diabetes based on specific diagnostic metrics provided in the collection. The selection of these cases from a wider database was subject to certain criteria. All of the patients here, in particular, are Pima Indian women over the age of 21 [3][4]

The objective of this application is to construct an e-diagnosis framework for diagnosing and classifying diabetes [5] [6] [7]. The system will be able to identify whether or not a person is at risk of developing diabetes based on multiple risk factors. Two supervised attribute selection methods with ranker were used to select five significant attributes, and two classification methods, 1) J48 decision Tree based classifier [8] and Naive Bayes, were used for comparing the results [9] .

2. Dataset Description

The Pima Indians diabetes data set contains eight causative features and one class label attribute. There are 9 columns and 768 rows in the dataset. 500 records are of non-diabetics and 268 are of diabetics. The binary classification result variable accepts (0 or 1) values, with 0 indicating a negative diabetes test and 1 indicating a positive diabetes test. The dataset characteristics (columns), descriptions, and basic statistics are shown in Table 1.

Table1: Dataset Description and Statistical Summary

Attributes	Min	Max	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Pregnancies	0	17	3.85	3	3.37
Glucose	0	199	120.89	117	31.97
Blood Pressure	0	122	69.11	72	19.36
Skin Thickness	0	99	20.54	23	15.95
Insulin	0	846	79.8	30.5	115.24
BMI	0	67.1	31.99	32	7.88
Diabetes Pedigree Function	0.078	2.42	0.47	0.3725	0.33
Age	21	81	33.24	29	11.76
Pregnancies	0	17	3.85	3	3.37
Glucose	0	199	120.89	117	31.97

3. Experimentation and Results

3.1 Featureselection:

Two supervised attribute selection filters with ranker methods were used for the selection of first five ranked attributes. These selected attributes were further used for the classification [10] [11].

A. SVM Attribute Selection: SVM classifier is used to determine the value of an attribute. The square of the weight given by the SVM is used to rank attributes. For multiclass scenarios, attribute selection is addressed by ranking attributes for each class separately using a one-vs-all technique and then, from the highest position of each pile to produce a final ranking.

B. Correlation Attribute Selection: This method measures the correlation using Pearson's correlation coefficient between an attribute and the class to determine its worth. By treating every value as an indicator, nominal qualities are considered value by value. A weighted average is used to calculate the overall correlation for a nominal property.

3.2 Classification:

A. J48 Classifier: J48 is an algorithm used for classification and prediction tasks. It is an implementation of the C4.5 algorithm, which was developed by Ross Quinlan. It is a decision tree algorithm that is commonly used for machine learning and data mining tasks where the goal is to classify data into one of several predefined classes or categories. Classification result is indicated by a leaf node in a decision tree and internal node represents attribute judgement.

B. Naïve Bayes Classifiers: Naive Bayes (NB) is both a descriptive and a predictive algorithm. The probabilities are descriptive before being used to predict the untrained data categories. This approach has various advantages, which are as follows. First and foremost, it is simple to use. Second, the amount of training data required by NB for classification is

not always large. Furthermore, despite the fact that the NB classifier is crudely written and its assumptions appear to be overly simplistic, it performs effectively in a variety of complex real-world scenarios.

3.3 Results of Machine Learning algorithms:

Table 2 shows the first five attributes selected by SVM Attribute Selection and Correlation Attribute Selection with Ranker method. First two attributes Glucose and BMI are the same by both the methods.

Table 2: Comparison of Attribute ranking by SVM Attribute Selection and Correlation Attribute Selection

Ranks	SVM and Ranker	Correlation and Ranker
1	Glucose	Glucose
2	BMI	BMI
3	Pregnancies	Age
4	Diabetes Pedigree Function	Pregnancies
5	Blood Pressure	Diabetes Pedigree Function

It is also observed that SVM selected Blood Pressure as an important attribute and Correlation found Age as an important attribute.

Table 3: Comparison of Classification Results

Attributes	SVM Attribute Selection		Correlation	Attribute Selection	
	J48	Naive Classifier	J48	Naive Classifier	Bayes
Correctly Classified Instances	570	589	575	597	
Incorrectly Classified Instances	198	179	193	171	
Accuracy	74.22%	76.69%	74.87%	77.73%	
Kappa statistic	0.4216	0.472	0.4235	0.4873	
Root mean squared error	0.4272	0.4059	0.4247	0.3999	
Root relative squared error	89.62%	85.16%	89.10%	83.90%	

Table 3 displays classification results obtained using J48 and Naive Bayes Classifier for the first five ranked attributes selected by Correlation Attribute Selection and SVM Attribute Selection. It is also observed that Naive Bayes Classifier demonstrated better results than J48 for both the attribute selectors

Figure 1 Classification Accuracy

4 Conclusion and future work

This research proposed a classification model comprises of supervised attribute selection methods with ranker that are appropriate for designing diagnostic systems of diabetic patients. Two machine learning supervised attribute selection techniques and two classifiers were used to train the models, which were then tested to predict if a subject's diabetes-related diagnosis is positive based on given attributes. However, for five ranked attributes selected using SVM and Nave Bayes classification model performs better the Correlation attribute selection and J48 decision tree models in terms of accuracy. We can conclude that a Nave Bayes model performs well for binary classification with a SVM attribute selection.

In the future, novel techniques can be implemented and utilizing them for various kinds of health care analysis. For instance, applying appropriate pre-processing methods for attribute selection may improve the accuracy. New automation and automated processes can be created for data collection which will enhance the prediction of other diseases and related medical conditions.

Conflicts of interest

We hereby declare that, we have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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